

Supplementary material for the article: *Statistical analysis of continuous outcomes from parallel-arm randomized controlled trials in nutrition – a tutorial*

An example of the statistical analysis using R

A recent study compared a diet consisting of more fruit and vegetables as well as other foods known to be associated with reduced risk of depression to a habitual control diet.¹ The primary outcome was the revised version of the Centre for Epidemiological Studies Depression scale (CESD-R) for measuring depressive symptoms; the CESD-R is integer-valued in the range from 0 to 60. It was measured at baseline and at end of study (after three 3 weeks). This outcome was used in this example. However, the example would work the same way for any other outcome reported in the study.

One inclusion criterion involved a secondary outcome, which seems to be correlated with the primary outcome CESD-R, such that only participants with moderate or high depression symptoms were included. Therefore it may be anticipated that the baseline distribution of some outcomes are truncated and covariate adjustment using baseline values will be useful. Simple randomization with 1:1 allocation was applied. There might be some small risk of baseline imbalance just by chance as the sample size was 101. Covariate adjustment included baseline CESD, age, BMI, and gender, which were available in the data file. The authors provided no arguments for including age, BMI, and gender. However, these covariates are often used and it should be possible to justify their use by referring to relevant literature. It should also be noted that only nearly complete-case data were provided in the data file. This means that no information was available on participants that were randomized but then dropped out except for a single participant where only CESD at baseline was provided.

For the sake of comparing results, both an ANCOVA model and an ANCOVA mixed model including participant-specific random effects were fitted. In reality the ANCOVA model would suffice as judged from what we learned about the trial design. Out of a total of 101 (51 in the diet group) only 76 (38 in both groups) participants provided data for the ANCOVA model whereas 77 participants provided data for the ANCOVA mixed model including participant-specific random effects. As the data contain almost no incomplete pairs it was expected that the two approaches would result in quite similar estimated differences and corresponding standard errors. It is also worth noting that the ANCOVA model even under model misspecification would provide an unbiased estimated difference and corresponding standard error due to the 1:1 allocation under simple randomization. The statistical analyses were carried out using the statistical environment **R**.²

ANCOVA model

The data file, which was in an Excel (xlsx) format, was downloaded from the web page <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0222768>. After conversion to a csv file (named "journal.pone.0222768.s003-1.csv"), it was imported into R using the following line (note the encoding of missing values #NULL! has to be specified; this is the encoding inherited from the Excel sheet):

```
francis.etal <- read.csv2(file.choose(), na.strings = "#NULL!")
```

To ensure that the data import was successful a few **R** functions for summarizing the data in different ways are useful for a first inspection. They summarize the data various (partly overlapping ways) in terms of 1) the numbers of rows and columns, 2) categorical and numeric variables, 3) descriptive statistics by column, and 4) the first rows of the data set (columns should be clearly discernible):

```
dim(francis.etal)
str(francis.etal)
summary(francis.etal)
head(francis.etal)
```

As the data import worked out fine, the next step is to ensure that relevant categorical variables are encoded as categorical variables (which is by default not the case if numbers were used to indicate categories). For the present data set, the variable named "Group" encoded for the 2 intervention groups using the numbers 1 (Diet change) and 2 (Habitual diet) and it was recoded into a categorical variable with more informative levels:

```
francis.etal[["Group"]] <- as.factor(francis.etal[["Group"]])
levels(francis.etal[["Group"]]) <- c("DC", "HD")
```

Now the ANCOVA model may be fitted using the **R** function `lm()` (which is short for linear model):

```
francis.etal.ANCOVA <- lm(D21CESD ~ Group + D1CESDTotal + D1BMI + Age + Gender,
                        data = francis.etal)
```

The order of terms on the right-hand side has the group variable, corresponding to the comparison of interest, coming first followed by the covariates baseline CESD, BMI, age, and gender. However, it could be any order: Estimates and standard errors would still remain the same.

Graphical model checking corresponds to looking at the residual plot and the QQ (quantile-quantile) plot obtained from the model fit. The residual plot is useful for assessing if the scatter of the residuals (that parts in the outcome values not explained by the statistical model, on the y axis) show the same spread or variation regardless of the magnitude of the fitted values (x axis). The QQ plot is used for assessing the normality assumption. Ideally the ordered standardized residuals should be close to the expected values when ranking random numbers generated from a standard normal distribution, which is the distribution that residuals should follow if model assumptions hold.

These two plots were obtained using the following two **R** lines:

```
plot(francis.etal.ANCOVA, which = 1) # residual plot
plot(francis.etal.ANCOVA, which = 2) # QQ plot
```

The resulting plots are shown in Supplementary Figure 1 (on purpose these plots were rendered in a simplistic format taken directly from the **R** output: they were for internal use, not for publication). The residual plot shows an even scatter above and below the x axis. The spread is a little less for small fitted values (left part of the plot), but it is too little deviation to question the model assumption on variance homogeneity. The QQ plot shows good agreement between (observed) residuals and theoretical, predicted values and there is no indication of any large departures from the normal distribution (agreement is less pronounced in the tails but it is only for a few data points). In short the graphical model checking supported the model assumptions of the ANCOVA model.

Now it is time to look at the output. The estimated difference and the corresponding standard error and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were retrieved from the model fit named `francis.etal.ANCOVA` using the generic **R** functions `summary()` and `confint()`:

```
coef(summary(francis.etal.ANCOVA))
confint(francis.etal.ANCOVA)
```

The resulting output looked like this:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.823059625	11.17638028	0.16311718	8.708962e-01
GroupHD	6.026164319	2.21408480	2.72174052	8.188250e-03
D1CESDTotal	0.555603718	0.07788271	7.13385187	7.117171e-10
D1BMI	0.224053458	0.37782325	0.59301131	5.550847e-01
Age	0.007790008	0.49240097	0.01582046	9.874226e-01
Gender	-2.284957809	2.34992763	-0.97235242	3.342233e-01

	2.5 %	97.5 %
(Intercept)	-20.4675280	24.1136472
GroupHD	1.6103114	10.4420172
D1CESDTotal	0.4002716	0.7109359
D1BMI	-0.5294913	0.9775982
Age	-0.9742728	0.9898528
Gender	-6.9717407	2.4018251

Change in diet compared to habitual diet led to a substantial reduction in the level of depression symptoms (note that the above results show the increase in CESD from the change in diet group to the habitual diet group, due to CD coming before HD in alphabetical order). Specifically, the change in diet group had an estimated average reduction in CESD of 6 (95% CI: [2, 10]) scores. Fitting an ANCOVA model only including the baseline CESD as covariate but not the other covariates, resulted in very similar results (slightly smaller standard error for the estimated difference), underlining the fact the baseline outcome is a powerful covariate.

Finally, in Supplementary Figure 2 the effect of including baseline CESD in the model was explored through two histograms, one showing the empirical distribution of CESD values at end of study and another one showing the distribution of CESD values at end of study after removal of the estimated covariate effect of the CESD values at baseline. It is noteworthy how a covariate can turn a right-skewed distribution into a symmetric, normal distribution.

In case model misspecification would be suspected the following **R** lines would provide the robust standard error for the estimated difference (using the **R** extension packages `lmtest` and `sandwich`, which were installed beforehand from the online repository CRAN; the function `library()` was used for activating the extension package):

```
library(lmtest)
library(sandwich)
coeftest(francis.etal.ANCOVA, vcov. = sandwich)
```

As there is no indication of model misspecification the robust standard error is close to the model-based standard error.

ANCOVA mixed model including participant-specific random effects

In order to fit a linear mixed model in **R** data have re-arranged into a long format such that there is one row per visit, meaning two rows per participants (baseline and end of study). The function `reshape()` is one of several options in **R** for re-arranging data sets. The following line achieved the conversion:

```
francis.etal.long <- reshape(francis.etal, varying = c("D1CESDTotal", "D21CESD"),
```

```
v.names = "CESD",
idvar = "ID", timevar = "Visit",
direction = "long")
```

The new data set in the long format contained additional columns with names ID, Visit, and CESD. The variable Visit was then recoded into a categorical variable, which is needed for the model specification:

```
francis.etal.long[["Visit"]] <- as.factor(francis.etal.long[["Visit"]])
```

The ANCOVA mixed model including participant-specific random effects was fitted using the **R** extension package lme4 (which was installed beforehand from the online repository CRAN).

```
library(lme4)
francis.etal.ANCOVA.mixed1 <- lmer(CESD ~ Group*Visit + D1BMI*Visit + Age*Visit +
                                Gender*Visit + (1|ID), data = francis.etal.long)
```

The function lmer() was used for fitting the linear mixed model. The model included the outcome on the left-hand side of the tilde and the group-visit interaction term, which is the key term used for comparing groups, as well as interaction terms corresponding to the covariate effects (they have to involve Visit as explained previously) as fixed effects and participant-specific random effects (the term (1|ID)) on the right-hand side of the tilde.

Again the first step was to assess the model assumptions, which are not exactly the same as for the ANCOVA model. The R function plot() and qqnorm() may be used for obtaining the residual and QQ plots.

```
plot(francis.etal.ANCOVA.mixed1)
qqnorm(residuals(francis.etal.ANCOVA.mixed1))
abline(a = 0, b = sd(residuals(francis.etal.ANCOVA.mixed1)), lty = "dotted")
```

The residual plot, which is shown in Supplementary Figure 3, looked much like the one for the ANCOVA model and the same comments apply. The QQ plot, however, showed more some departure from normality due to the pronounced curvature in the middle range. This observation indicates that the linear mixed model is struggling more with the right-skewed outcome values than the ANCOVA model was.

For extracting the estimated difference, the corresponding standard error and confidence interval, the **R** extension package multcomp is useful:

```
library(multcomp)
francis.etal.glht <- glht(francis.etal.ANCOVA.mixed1)
confint(francis.etal.glht, calpha = 1.96)
```

The argument calpha = 1.96 ensured that no multiplicity adjustment of the width of the confidence intervals was applied.

The output looked like this:

	Estimate	lwr	upr
(Intercept) == 0	33.6794	3.8351	63.5236
GroupHD == 0	-0.2138	-6.3525	5.9249
Visit2 == 0	-13.4135	-38.8423	12.0153

D1BMI == 0	-0.1522	-1.2006	0.8962
Age == 0	-0.3904	-1.7624	0.9815
Gender == 0	-1.2981	-7.7720	5.1759
GroupHD:Visit2 == 0	6.0764	0.8619	11.2908
Visit2:D1BMI == 0	0.2983	-0.5909	1.1874
Visit2:Age == 0	0.1827	-0.9761	1.3414
Visit2:Gender == 0	-1.6481	-7.1667	3.8705

The diet group had an estimated average reduction in the CESD of 6 (95% CI: [1, 11]) scores (taken from the line GroupHD:Visit2 == 0, which reports the estimated difference in changes from baseline to end of study for the two groups). The confidence interval turned out to be somewhat larger than for the ANCOVA model. Just like for the above ANCOVA model, only utilizing the baseline CESD but no additional covariates resulted in very similar results.

A more direct way of understanding the output would be to specify the difference of changes explicitly as shown below. It requires fitting the linear mixed model once more in a different parameterization where the group and visit variables have been combined into a single variable (named GrXVi below) with as many levels as there combinations.

```
francis.etal.long[["GrXVi"]] <- with(francis.etal.long, interaction(Group, Visit))

francis.etal.ANCOVA.mixed.2 <- lmer(CESD ~ GrXVi-1 + D1BMI*Visit + Age*Visit +
  Gender*Visit + (1|ID), data = francis.etal.long)
coef(summary(francis.etal.ANCOVA.mixed.2))
```

The last line above is merely to see the naming used for the 4 combinations; these names are used below to explicitly specify the difference of changes (again using the function glht() from the package "multcomp"):

```
francis.etal.glhtObject2 <-
glht(francis.etal.ANCOVA.mixed.2,
  linfct = c("GrXViDC.2 - GrXViDC.1 - GrXViHD.2 - GrXViHD.1 = 0"))

confint(francis.etal.glhtObject2, calpha = 1.96)
```

The resulting output looked like this (only showing the relevant part):

	Estimate	lwr	upr
GrXViDC.2 - GrXViDC.1 - GrXViHD.2 - -GrXViHD.1 == 0	-6.0764	-11.2908	-0.8619

The result is the same as above but this time it shows directly that the change in diet ("DC") group experienced a reduction in CESD compared to the habitual diet group ("HD"). This last approach is also applicable in case there are more than two intervention groups (in contrast to the first approach described above using the interaction term Group*Visit).

References

- Francis, H. M., Stevenson, R. J., Chambers, J. R., Gupta, D., Newey, B., Lim, C. K. (2019). A brief diet intervention can reduce symptoms of depression in young adults – A randomised controlled trial. *PLoS ONE*, **14**, e0222768. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0222768>
- R Core Team (2020). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org>

Supplementary Figure 1

Supplementary Figure 2

Supplementary Figure 3

